

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Tensile Properties of Nano Cellulose Reinforced Silkworm Silk Composite Fibers

Chen Wu, Hiroki Kurita, Zhenjin Wang and Fumio Narita
Tohoku university Materials Processing Department

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Catalog

1. Introduction
2. Experimental
3. Results and discussion
4. Summary and future plans

1. Introduction

Cellulose reinforced composite silkworm silk fiber

Matrix: Silkworm silk fiber

- A natural fiber commonly used in daily life
- A conventional material which has been used over 1000 years

Reinforcement: Cellulose nanofiber (CNF)

- A nanomaterial with excellent mechanical properties
- Widely used as reinforcement in composite material

1. Introduction

Conventional approaches

- Use of toxic chemical solvent
- Harmful to both human's health and environment

New approach: CNF diets

- Obtain tougher fibers directly
- Safe and eco-friendly

2. Experimental

1. Equations

2. Experimental setup

3. Experimental procedure

2.1 Equations

- Young's modulus(E)

$$E = \sigma / \varepsilon$$

Where,

σ ...stress, uniaxial force per unit surface

ε ...strain, change in length divided by original length

- Ultimate tensile strength(σ_b)

$$\sigma_b = F_b / S_o$$

Where,

F_b ...maximum force before breaking

S_o ...surface at maximum force

2.2 Experimental setup

Specimen

Speed: 20 mm/min

Fig.2 Tensile test

2.3 Experimental procedure

1. Material preparation
2. Characterization and tensile property studies

2.3.1 Material preparation

1. Divide the silkworm into 3 group
2. Raise the silkworms with different diets(as following) until they made cocoons
3. Collect the silk fibers from cocoons

The diets fed to different groups

- ① Normal diets(0 wt.% CNF)
- ② Diets with 5 wt.% CNF
- ③ Diets with 10 wt.% CNF

Fig.1 (a) Silk worm and diet with CNF; (b) cocoons

2.3.2 Morphology characterization and tensile property studies

Morphology characterization

- Scanning probe machine
- Scanning electron machine

Tensile property

- Tensile tester

3. Results and discussion

1. CNF separation
2. Cross-sectional area measurement
3. Numerical analysis
4. Discussion

3.1 CNF separation

2D
images

3D
images

CNF 0 wt.%

CNF 5 wt.%

CNF 10 wt.%

Fig.5 Scanning probe microscope(SPM) images

3.2 Cross-sectional area measurement

Group name

CNF 0 wt.%

CNF 5 wt.%

CNF 10 wt.%

Cross-sectional area

$393.05 \mu m^2$

$271.74 \mu m^2$

$356.05 \mu m^2$

Fig.3 Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images

3.3 Numerical analysis

Stress-strain curves

During elastic deformation

$$E = \sigma / \varepsilon$$

The young's modulus and the fracture strength of

5 wt.% CNF/silk composite fiber was improved compare to the pure silk fiber

10 wt.% CNF/silk composite fiber changes little from pure silk fiber

Fig.3 Stress-strain curves

3.3 Numerical analysis

Tensile property calculation

Fig.4 (a)Young's modulus and (b)ultimate tensile strength

3.4 Discussion

- The agglomeration of CNFs causes stress concentration within the fibers.
- The damage at the interface between the CNFs and the silk matrix leading to the limited load transfer across the interface
- There is a critical CNF content for silk fiber reinforcement

4. Summary and future plans

- CNF/Silk composite fibers can be obtained directly by adding CNF into the silkworms' diets
- The young's modulus and the fracture strength can be gained nonlinearly by increasing the weight fraction of CNF in silkworms' diets
- In the further work, we will look for the most suitable content of CNF in silkworms' diets and the evaluations will be operated with the degummed silk fibers .

Thank you for your attention!